

Regional-scale prospectivity analysis of northern Finland for CRMs hosted in ultramafic-mafic orthomagmatic deposits

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Metals such as nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), platinum group metals (PGMs), vanadium (V), and copper (Cu) are termed either critical raw materials (CRMs) or strategic raw materials by the European Union due to rising projected demand in modern industrial value chains in strategic and environmentally friendly industries and potential short supply (European Commission, 2023). Therefore, it is crucial to be self-reliant and produce such raw materials locally. The SEMACRET project aims to develop responsible exploration techniques for such CRMs to ensure a consistent supply for the transition to green energy.

Northern Finland is known to host the above-listed CRMs in ultramafic- mafic intrusions of two sub-types: conduit-type, sulphide-rich Ni-Cu-(PGM)-(Co) deposits and layered mafic intrusion type, relatively sulphide-poor PGM-Cr-V-(Co)-(Ni)-(Cu) deposits. This study describes computer-based prospectivity analyses for both these deposit types using Fuzzy Inference Systems (FIS), a supervised, knowledge-based symbolic artificial intelligence technique. The multi-stage FIS used in the study rely on generalised conceptual mineral systems models for each of the two deposit types. These mineral systems models are also used to identify the targeting criteria for the two deposit types. The main components of the conduit-type mineral system include (1) Primitive, mantle-derived, magnesium-rich rocks (ultramafic and mafic rocks), which are the primary source of metal; (2) trans-lithospheric faults and chonoliths that serve as pathways of magma, locally enhanced by varying compressional/extensional tectonic regimes; and (3) dilatational zones of high, fracture-related permeability and localised structures that act as physical traps; along with abundant sulphur-rich crustal rocks that can provide the external sulphur required to form immiscible sulphide melts (Cawthorn et al., 2005; Maier, 2005; Maier and Groves, 2011; Joly et al., 2015). The mineral systems model of the layered mafic intrusion type deposits differs only in the third: traps component, wherein the magma is trapped within the cratonic lithosphere as large magma chambers, forming a layered sequence of ultramafic to mafic rocks due to fractional crystallisation under low regional stress and limited magma-induced sagging. Mineralisation occurs as contact style (or marginal type at the base of the intrusion) and reef type between the lower ultramafic zone and the upper mafic zone and among mafic rocks (Cawthorn et al., 2005; Maier, 2005; Maier and Groves, 2011).

Targeting criteria representing the crucial processes of the respective mineral system were mapped using their spatial proxies from various geoscientific datasets. They were then represented as GIS predictor maps, derived using spatial analyses and geoprocessing tools. New innovative predictor maps have been attempted in this study. The predictor maps of the two mineral systems were integrated into their respective multi-stage FIS structured on their mineral systems model to obtain the prospectivity maps. The resultant prospectivity maps show good agreement with their respective deposits. Remarkably, despite the two mineral systems being broadly similar, the prospectivity models can distinguish between the two types and demarcate promising regions for further detailed exploration.

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References

- European Commission (2023). Study on the critical raw materials for the EU 2023.
- Maier, W.D., (2005). Platinum-group element (PGE) deposits and occurrences: Mineralization styles, genetic concepts, and exploration criteria. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 41(3), pp.165-191.
- Maier, W.D. and Groves, D.I., (2011). Temporal and spatial controls on the formation of magmatic PGE and Ni-Cu deposits. *Mineralium Deposita*, 46, pp.841-857.
- Cawthorn, R.G., Barnes, S.J., Ballhaus, C. and Malitch, K.N., (2005). Platinum group element, chromium, and vanadium deposits in mafic and ultramafic rocks.
- Joly, A., Porwal, A., McCuaig, T.C., Chudasama, B., Dentith, M.C. and Aitken, A.R., (2015). Mineral systems approach applied to GIS-based 2D-prospectivity modelling of geological regions: Insights from Western Australia. *Ore Geology Reviews*, 71, pp.673-702.